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EVALUATION OF ANTI-CANCER ACTIVITY IN METHANOLIC EXTRACT OF *ENICOSTEMMA LITTORALE* ON DEN INDUCED HEPATOCARCINOGENESIS IN RATS

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ABSTRACT

The present study is aimed at evaluating the chemoprotective effect of *Enicostemma littorale* in DEN induced hepato-carcinogenesis in Sprague Dawley rats. The preliminary steps involved extraction, phytochemical investigation, HPTLC study and *In vitro* antioxidant activity using DPPH, ABTS. and Initiation of HCC was done by single i.p injection of DEN at a dose of 200mg/kg. The MEEL received treatment for 90 days after 14 days of development of HCC and continued for entire study period, whereas the other two group given normal saline, 5-fluorouracil (20mg/kg) i.p. The results showed that the injection DEN lead to the development of liver tumors in rats. Significant effect of serum biochemical parameter like SGOT, SGPT, ALP, UREA, TOTAL PROTEIN and tumor marker was observed with depletion of endogenous antioxidants SOD, CAT, GSH, there by leading to higher LPO. The result exhibited that MEEL treatment (Preventive) group offered excellent shielding against HCC and displayed all the parameter in near normal range with a maintained antioxidant enzyme system. The result obtained showed that extracts were found to containing phenols at a concentration of 70.25 mg/g and flavonoids 26.03mg/g. HPTLC Analysis showed presence of Quercetin, Mangiferin, Gallic acid, Catechin and sweroside. In the DPPH, ABTS, FRAP, TRAP radical scavenging assay MEEL has displayed the highest antiradical activity in both assays and was also comparable with the standard quercetin The present study reveal the efficacy of the MEEL to prevent malignancy induced by chemical carcinogen and the phytoconstituents responsible for activity.

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INTRODUCTION

Cancer is a group of many related diseases that begin in cells, the body's basic unit of life. Normally, cells grow and divide to produce more cells only when the body needs them. Sometimes, however, cells become abnormal and keep dividing to form more cells without control or order, creating a mass of excess tissue called a tumor. Tumors can be malignant (cancerous) or benign (non cancerous). Cancer is a group of disease involving abnormal cell growth with the potential to invade (or) spread to other part of the body. It result from variation in normal mechanism governing cell behavior [1] Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) is the most common type of primary liver cancer and is the most common cause of death in people with cirrhosis. It occurs in the setting of chronic liver inflammation, and is most closely linked to chronic viral hepatitis infection (or) exposure to toxin such as alcohol. They are either primary when the cancer starts in itself, or metastatic, when the cancer has spread to liver from some other part of the body[2] *Enicostemma littorale* Blume (*E. littorale*) plays a vital role in human healthcare. The plant parts of *E. littorale* such as leaves, roots were used in traditional practice for treating several ailments like malaria, skin diseases, leprosy, diabetes etc. The leaf possesses hypoglycemic, antioxidant, hepatoprotective and hepatomodulatory properties and helps in reducing obesity[3] DEN (diethyl nitrosamine) is a well known hepatocarcinogenic agent, which produces the primary metabolic activation resulting in initiation of liver carcinogenesis and formation of liver tumor after repeated administration, is normally used to induce liver cancer in several animal models[4].The present study was aimed to evaluate the anti-cancer Activity in methanolic extract of *Enicostemma littorale* on DEN Induced hepatocarcinogenesis in rats and detection and estimation of phytoconstituents responsible for therapeutic efficacy.

Figure 1: Habitat of *Enicostemma littorale* Blume.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant collection, authentication and extraction

The whole plant *Enicostemma littorale* were collected from the area of Thirunelveli, Tamilnadu, India. The plant material was authenticated by Dr.P.Sathiyarajeswaran, Director, Plant Anatomy Research Centre, Chennai, Tamilnadu, India and a voucher specimen no: E18020901L of the whole plant. Dried and coarse powder of *Enicostemma littorale* (400g) were extracted successively using methanol as a solvent, it was extracted in Soxhle. Extract was concentrated to dryness in rotary evaporator under reduced pressure to yield a dark brown mass of methanolic extract of *Enicostemma littorale* (MEEL) plant. The obtained crude extract was weighed and stored. The percentage of yield - 38.3 %.

Preliminary phytochemical analysis

A portion of extract was subjected to preliminary phytochemical analysis to confirm the presence of carbohydrates, alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, proteins, aminoacids, tannins and steroids[5].

Quantification of Total Phenolics and Flavonoids

Estimation of Total Phenolics

The total phenolic content of the extract was determined by Folin-Ciocalteu assay method[6]. To an aliquot 100µl of extract (or standard solution of Gallic acid (10, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100µg/ml) added 50µl of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent followed by 860µl of distilled water and the mixture is incubated for 5min at room temperature. 100µl of 20% sodium carbonate and 890µl of distilled water were added to make the final solution to 2ml. It was incubated for 30min in dark to complete the reaction. The absorbance of the mixture was measured at 725nm against blank. Distilled water was used as reagent blank. The tests were performed in triplicate to get mean the values. The total phenolic content was found out from the calibration curve of Gallic acid and it was conveyed as milligrams of Gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per gram of extract.

Estimation of Total Flavonoids

The total flavonoid content of the MEEL was determined by using Aluminium chloride colorimetric method[7]. To an aliquot of 100µl of extract or standard solutions of Quercetin (10, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100µg/ml), methanol was added separately to make up the solution upto 2ml. The resulting mixture was treated with 0.1ml of 10% aluminium chloride, 0.1ml of 1M potassium acetate and 2.8ml of distilled water. Shaken well and incubated at room temperature for 30minutes. The absorbance was measured at 415nm against blank, where a solution of 2ml ethanol, 0.1ml potassium acetate, 2.8ml distilled water and 0.1ml of aluminium chloride serve as blank solution. The total flavonoid content was determined from the standard Quercetin calibration curve and it was expressed as milligrams of Quercetin equivalents (QE) per gram of extract.

High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography

Preparation of standard and sample

HPTLC was used for the qualitative and quantitative phytochemical study of herbal drugs. Stock solutions of standard compounds were prepared by dissolving accurately weighed 1mg of Gallic acid, Rutin, Quercetin, Maniferin, and Gallic acid in 1ml of methanol (HPTLC grade). Samples were prepared by accurately weighed 1g of *Enicostemma littorale* and dissolved separately in 10ml methanol. Each sample was then filtered by using Whatmann No.1 filter paper.

Application of sample

The sample solution were spotted in the form of bands of width 6mm with a Hamilton 100µl syringe on percolated plate 60 F254 (10 cm × 10 cm with 0.2 mm thickness) using a camag Linomat V applicator. The slit dimension was kept 6 mm × 0.45 mm. 10µl of each sample and 5µl of standard solutions were applied on to the plate .

Development

The chromatogram was development in Camag glass twin through chamber (10 × 10 cm) previously saturated with the mobile phase Toluene: Ethyl acetate: Formic acid: Methanol (3:6:1.6:0.4) mobile phase was used for quantification of flavonoids and mobile phase of ethyl acetate: methanol: water (7.7:1.5:0.5) was used for quantification of sweroside[8]. The migration distance was 80 mm TLC plate were air dried with air dryer. Densitometry scanning was performed using Camag TLC Scanner III at 254 nm and 366 nm operated by a wincat software.

Detection

The plate was scanned at UV 254 nm using Camag TLC Scanner- III. Rf value of each compound which were separated on plate and data of peak area of each band was recorded .

In vitro antioxidant studies

DPPH radical scavenging assay

The antioxidant activity of the extract was measured in terms of hydrogen donating or radical scavenging ability, using the DPPH method. 0.1mM solution of DPPH in methanol was prepared and 1ml of this solution was added to 1ml of various concentrations of sample and the reference compound (10, 20, 30, 40 and 50µg/ml). The mixture was shaken vigorously and left to stand in the dark at room temperature for 30 min. Then the absorbance was measured at 517nm against a blank. Reference compound used was ascorbic acid. A control reaction was carried out without the test sample [9]. The percentage of inhibition was calculated by comparing the absorbance values of the control and test samples. Antiradical activity was expressed as percentage inhibition (%) and calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Percentage inhibition (I \%)} = (\text{Abs control} - \text{Abs sample} / \text{Abs control}) \times 100$$

ABTS radical cation assay

ABTS radical scavenging activity of the extract was measured by the method. ABTS was dissolved in water to a 7mM concentration. ABTS radical cation (ABTS⁺) was produced by reacting ABTS stock solution with 2.45mM potassium persulfate and allowing the mixture to stand in the dark at room temperature for 12 - 16h before use. For the study, ABTS solution was diluted with phosphate buffer saline pH 7.4 (PBS) to an absorbance of 0.70 (± 0.02) at 734nm and equilibrated at 300°C[10]. After addition of 2ml of diluted ABTS⁺ solution to 20µl of various concentrations of sample or reference compound (ascorbic acid), the reaction mixture was incubated for 6min and then absorbance was measured at 734nm against a blank. A control reaction was carried out without the sample. The percentage inhibition of ABTS⁺ by the sample was calculated according to the formula:

$$\text{Percentage inhibition (I \%)} = (\text{Abs control} - \text{Abs sample} / \text{Abs control}) \times 100.$$

Ferric reducing anti-oxidant power assay (FRAP)

The basic principle involved in the assay is the reduction of the ferric complex of Fe(TPTZ)³⁺ i.e: tripyridyltriazine (a ferroin analogue) to Fe(TPTZ)²⁺ complex (intensely blue in colour) in the presence of anti-oxidant in an acidic pH. There will be an increase in absorbance value at 593nm [10]. The reagent was prepared by mixing 15.15ml 0.2M acetate buffer (pH 3.6), 1.5ml of 20mMol TPTZ, 1.5ml of 20mMol ferric chloride and 1.9ml of distilled water. The sample /standard compounds were taken in different concentrations of (20,40,60,80 and 100µg/ml) and mixed with 0.9ml of the reagent. Absorbance of the mixture was measured spectrophotometrically at 595nm after 30minutes of incubation. Vitamin-C was used as standard. The experiment was done in duplicate and parallel blank was also prepared excluding the sample/standard compound.

Total reducing antioxidant power assay (TRAP)

The reagent was prepared by mixing 5ml DCF (2,7-dichlorofluorescein acetate) of, 20ml of PBS (Sodium phosphate buffer saline), 25ml of NaOH. The sample /standard compounds were taken in different concentrations of (20,40,60,80 and 100 µg/ml) and mixed with 0.9ml of the reagent. Absorbance of the mixture was measured spectrophotometrically at 490nm after 30 minutes of incubation[10]. Vitamin-C was used as standard. The experiment was done in duplicate and parallel blank was also prepared excluding the sample/standard compound.

Pharmacological study

Experimental animals

Sprague Dawley Male rat weight of animals was 150-200gm. The animals were housed under controlled conditions of temperature (20-25°C) and photoperiod 12-h light/dark cycle. All animal procedures were performed after approval from the animal ethical committee and accordance with the recommendations for the proper care and use of laboratory animals[11-14].

Screening of anti-cancer activity of MEEL

Group 1 - Normal (Normal saline)

Group 2- DEN Control

Group 3- DEN + Standard [5 Flurouracil (20 mg/kg) body wt *i.p*]

Group 4- DEN + MEEL (Low dose – 250 mg/kg *p.o*)

Group 5- DEN + MEEL (High dose – 500 mg/kg *p.o*)

Estimation of haematological parameters

Blood collection

After the end of the treatment period (90 days) the animals were anaesthetized with ketamine (*i.p*) and its blood was collected by retro orbital puncture with addition of EDTA for the enumeration of blood cells *i.e.*, RBC and WBC. The estimation of various biochemical parameters carried out by using blood sample without adding EDTA.

Separation of Serum

For the estimation of the biochemical parameters such as Alkaline phosphatase (ALP), Serum glutamate oxalo acetate transaminase (SGOT), Serum glutamate pyruvate transaminase (SGPT), Serum creatinine and total protein, the serum was separated from the blood by centrifuging at 5000 rpm for 15 minutes. The separated serum was collected and used for the estimation of parameters.

Evaluation of Antioxidant Parameters

A 10% homogenate of liver tissue was used to analysis enzymatic antioxidant activity like superoxide dismutase (SOD) Catalase (CAT), and non enzymatic anti oxidant activity reduced glutathione activity (GSH), and lipid peroxidation (LPO) were also estimated[15-16].

Histopathological studies

The liver from all groups were removed rapidly, and thoroughly rinsed with ice-cold saline. After 24hr of fixation followed by embedding in a paraffin block, it was cut into sections of 5µ onto a glass slide and stained with hematoxylin-eosin for histological assessment of the tissue. Sections of liver were examined by light microscope at 10X and 40X magnification[17].

Statistical analysis

The data's of all the parameters were analyzed using the Graph pad 5.0 software. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA); one way ANOVA followed by Tukey multiple comparison test was performed. The values were expressed as Mean ± SEM.

RESULT AND DISSCUSION

Preliminary phytochemical analysis

From the phytochemical results shows the presence of Carbohydrates, Glycosides, Alkaloids, Phenolics, Flavonoids, Tannins, Triterpenoids, Saponins, Steroids, Proteins and amino acids in the formulation.

Estimation of Total Phenol and Flavanoids in MEEL

The preliminary phytochemical analysis showed the presence of phenols and flavonoids in plant extract which are considered as potent antioxidants. The total phenol and flavonoids was determined by UV spectrophotometric method. The result obtained showed that extracts were found to containing phenols at a concentration of 70.25 mg/g and flavonoids 26.03mg/g.

High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography :

The following different solvent compositions were tried for monitoring the elution of components in the plant extract of *Enicostemma litrolle*. Toluene: Ethyl acetate: Formic acid: Methanol (3:6:1.6:0.4) were used for quantification of flavonoids in the extract and Ethyl acetate: methanol: water (7.7:1.5:0.5) were used for quantification of sweroside and the respective Rf values of flavanoids was found to be Quercetin 0.84, Mangiferin 0.26, Gallic acid 0.74, Catechin 0.74, and for sweroside 0.49

Figure 2: Chromatogram of extract and flavonoid standard standard sweroside marker

1. Quercetin (5µl), 2. MEEL (10µl)
3. Rutin (5µl) 4. Mangiferin (5µl)
5. Gallic acid (5µl), 6. Catechin (5µl)

Figure 3: Chromatogram of extract and markers.

1. MEEL (5µl), 2. MEEL (10µl) 3. MEEL (20µl)
4. Sweroside (20µl)

Table 1: Quantification of flavonoids and sweroside in MEEL.

Extract	Volume applied µl	Percentage of Quercetin	Percentage of mangiferin	Percentage of Gallic acid	Percentage of Catechin	Percentage of sweroside
MEEL	5µl	1.076%	0.15%	0.35%	0.56%	1.20%

***In vitro* Antioxidant Activity**

The methanolic extract of *Enicostemma littorle* was compared with standard markers to evaluate their antioxidant capacity using DPPH photometric assay, ABTS radical scavenging activity, Ferric reducing ability (FRAP) and TRAP. Table 2 indicates the IC₅₀ values of standard and the MEEL. The methanolic extract of *Enicostemma littorle* exhibited significant free radical scavenging activity of ABTS.

Table 2: Antioxidant potential of standard and Methanolic extract of *Enicostemma littorale*.

Assay	IC ₅₀ value	
	Standard	Sample
ABTS (Quercetin)	0.2013	13.44
DPPH (Quercetin)	5.981	33.74
FRAP (Quercetin)	28.17	48.64
TRAP (Quercetin)	16.81	49.63

PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITY

Haematological parameters

The results of hematological investigation show the disease control group has shown a significant reduction in RBC and WBC. The MEEL preventive group as well as treatment group has shown a significant increase of RBC. Table 3 indicate significant difference between the treated and control group.

Effect of Body weight and liver weight analysis

The results revealed that the body weights were significantly decreased in DEN treated group. However, extract treatment showed significant protection in body weight when compared to DEN control group. Standard drug also significantly increased the body weight than the DEN treated animals but no significant difference was observed between extract treated animals and standard treated animals. (Table 4). Liver weight were significantly increased in DEN control group. However, extract treatment group are showing significant production in liver weight .whereas , Standard drug show significant reduction in relative liver weight compared to DEN control group. (Table 5).

Serum biochemical parameters

Serum biochemical parameters clearly evident that DEN treatment group caused significant elevation of liver serum markers. DEN treated group, the level of AST, ALP, ALT, Urea, Creatinine were significantly elevated. The extract treatment was able to reverse all the elevated serum biochemical parameter near to normal and the results were comparable to that of standard treated group. (Table 6).

In vivo antioxidant studies

Administration of DEN induced control group increase in the level of lipid peroxidation and decrease in catalase, superoxide dismutase, glutathione peroxidase and glutathione S- transferase levels in liver homogenate. The MEEL preventive group manifested remarkable increase in their level which was extremely significant even more than that observed with standard group. (Table 7).

Table 3: Effect of MEEL on the RBC& WBC counts.

Groups	Normal	Control	Standard	MEEL Low dose	MEEL High dose
RBC	9.48 ±0.18	5.81 ±0.21***	8.78 ±0.07***	7.45 ±0.12***	6.73 ±0.08**
WBC	6.57 ±0.06	5.25 ±0.15***	6.59 ±0.12***	5.81 ±0.06**	5.30 ±0.05 ^{ns}

Data is expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6 animal in each group).

*** - P<0.001, **-P<0.001, *- P<0.05, ns- non Significant.

Table 4: Effect of MEEL on the Body weight of the Experimental rats.

Weight in gram	Normal	Control	Standard	MEEL Low dose	MEEL High dose
Initial body weight	145.7 ± 5.5	182.5 ±6.3***	129.3 ±5.2***	139.2 ±4.9***	149.5 ±3.4**
Final body weight	192.3 ±4.8	167.2 ±4.0**	185.3 ±3.5**	196 ±4.5***	205 ±5.9**

Data is expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6 animal in each group).

*** - P<0.001, **-P<0.001, *- P<0.05, ns- non Significant.

Liver weight analysis

Table 5: Effect of the MEEL on the Liver weight of the Experimental rats.

GROUP	Normal	Control	Standard	MEEL Low dose	MEEL High dose
Liver weight in gm	8.23 ±0.23	9.58 ±0.17***	8.13 ±0.21***	7.83 ±0.18**	7.03 ±0.26**

Data is expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6 animal in each group).

*** - P<0.001, **-P<0.001, *- P<0.05, ns- non Significant.

Table 6: Effect of the MEEL on the Serum biochemical parameters.

GROUP	Normal	Control	Standard	MEEL Low dose	MEEL High dose
SGOT(U/L)	44.5 ±1.176	83.67 ±1.282***	64.67 ±1.054***	66 ±1.366***	61 ±1.317**
SGPT(U/L)	37.5 ±1.893	87.33 ±2.459***	60.83 ±1.778**	74.67 ±1.116**	69.01 ±1.392**
ALP(U/L)	93.5 ±5.847	163 ±6.593***	99.67 ±4.372***	138.5 ±2.045*	135.1 ±2.162**
UREA	32.1 ±4.861	71.65 ±3.593***	46.17 ±4.045**	49.83 ±1.138**	43.68 ±1.352*
CREATININE (mg/dl)	0.67 ±0.060	1.65 ±0.076***	0.70 ±0.027***	0.73 ±0.044***	0.78 ±0.020***
PROTEIN (g/ml)	4.38 ±0.252	7.35 ±0.286***	5.84 ±0.120**	5.48 ±0.310**	6.93 ±0.188ns

Data is expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6 animal in each group).

*** - P<0.001, **-P<0.001, *- P<0.05, ns- non Significant.

Table 7: Estimation of enzymatic and non enzymatic activity.

Group	Normal	Control	Standard	MEEL Low dose	MEEL High dose
SOD (U/min/mg/ protein)	8.04 ±0.358	2.52 ±0.365***	6.63 ±0.435***	7.34 ±0.270***	6.97 ±0.276**
CAT (µmol of H ₂ O ₂ consumed/ min/mg protein)	75.97 ±4.499	35.67 ±4.499**	69.33 ±2.603***	54.17 ±5.839*	57.17 ±2.971**
LPO (nmol MDA / mg protein)	1.34 ±0.766	6.33 ±0.432***	4.70 ±0.171*	4.60 ±0.088ns	3.77 ±0.197*
GSH (mmoles/mg tissue protein)	9.37 ±0.308	3.98 ±0.279***	8.44 ±0.308**	6.97 ±0.303**	6.63 ±0.608*

Data is expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6 animal in each group)

*** - P<0.001, **-P<0.001, *- P<0.05, ns- non Significant

ESTIMATION OF HISTOPATHOLOGY

Figure 4 : Normal group showing the no evidence of inflammation and liver fibrosis.

Figure 5 : DEN induced control group showing Portal tract inflammation are present. Parenchymal necrosis (Focal lytic necrosis) was also evident .

Figure 6: Standard drug treated group showing Mild Portal inflammation No evidence of parenchymal inflammation / necrosis .

Figure 7:MEEL treated low dose group showing Portal tract – Inflammation Present. Hepatic parenchyma – Mild necrosis.

Figure 8: MEEL high dose treated group showing Portal inflammation with interface hepatitis .Parenchymal marked inflammation.

DISSCUSSION

This study demonstrate a potential role of methanolic extract of *Enicostemma littorale* in limiting pre neoplastic changes in DEN-initiated experimental hepatocarcinogenesis in rats. The result obtained showed that extracts were found to containing phenols at a concentration of 70.25 mg/g and flavonoids 26.03mg/g. In the present study the HPTLC Analysis revel the presence of Quercetin, Mangiferin, Rutin, Gallic acid & Catechin. Earlier report shows the iridoid glycoside sweroside was isolated from *Swertia mileensis* have antihepatitic activity and sweroside reduced the SGPT level in hepatitis patients after 45 days treatment[18-19] The effective cure rate for acute patients was 84% and that for chronic patients 70%. In the DPPH, ABTS, FRAP, TRAP radical scavenging assay MEEL has displayed the highest antiradical activity in both assays and was also comparable with the standard qucertain. Increase in liver weight was observed for the disease control group and the marked reduction of weight was observable in both preventive and treated groups of MEEL. Alterations were seen in the hematological parameters in HCC. The disease control group has shown a significant reduction in RBC and WBC. The MEEL preventive group as well as treatment group has shown a significant increase of RBC. The experimental group showed significant increase in WBC count while the treated group showed moderate reduction in WBC. Serum biochemical parameters show an altered pattern in the cancerous condition. The escalation in the activities of plasma AST, ALT, and ALP indicated that DEN may prompt hepatic dysfunction. The enzymes directly associated with the conversion of amino acids to keto acids are AST and ALT, and are proved to be increased in the HCC condition.

Serum transaminases, alkaline phosphatases, total bilirubin, creatinine, urea and a tumor marker enzyme alpha feto protein were evaluated MEEL treatment group was also very effective in normalizing the SGPT, creatinine and urea level, but only a moderately significant reduction was shown for the other parameters. Total Protein present in the liver tissue of disease control group was reduced due to the cancerous condition. But in the MEEL preventive group there was a significant increase in the protein levels compared to disease control and no noticeable difference when compared to the normal control. MEEL treatment group also exhibited significant increase in the protein content, bringing back it to the normal. The impaired liver functions may be due to oxidative stress which leads to disturbances in the protective physiological moieties that further leads to lipid peroxidation thus eventually causes damage to the macromolecules in vital biomembranes. There was a marked reduction in the activity of enzymatic as well as non-enzymatic components such as SOD, CAT, *and GSH in the disease control group, while it's note worthy that the MEEL preventive group manifested remarkable increase in their level which was extremely significant even more than that observed with standard group. The MEEL treatment group also displayed significant rise in all component levels. The results obtained from the current study demonstrate that the MEEL offers a significant protection against hepatocarcinoma and it was very clear that the extract was able to prevent malignancy. It was clear that there exists an antioxidants, When the MEEL groups received showed higher shielding in DEN induced HCC rat model. When the extract was given for prevention and treatment of cancer, the extract has manifested propitious results which may be on account of the additive activity of the phyto molecules present in the extracts.

CONCLUSION

The present study it can be concluded that the *Enicostemma littorale* Blume has the potential to prevent HCC as well as it can reduce the complications of the same. It seems promising that these data obtained from the study can be further validated in the future studies which eventually can be developed as a formulation that offers a high degree of protection from HCC. Further study is required for the detected compound sweroside and its mechanism of action for anticancer activity and for future use.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors Disclose no conflicts of interest for publication of manuscript.

ABBREVIATION USED

Abbreviation	Full name/ Meaning
MEEL	Methanolic extract of <i>Enicostemma littorale</i>
HCC	Hepatocellular Carinoma
DEN	Diethylnitrosamine
ROS	Reactive Oxygen Species
GSH	Reduced Glutathione
SOD	Superoxide Dimutase
CAT	Catalase
LPO	Lipid Peroxidase
SGOT	Serum Glutamate Oxaloacetate Transminase
SGPT	Serum Glutamate Pyruvate Transaminase
<i>p.o</i>	Per Oral
<i>i.p</i>	Intra peritoneal
µl	Micro Litre
ml	Milli Litre
g	Gram
kg	Kilo gram
ANOVA	Anaysis of Variance
SEM	Standard Error Mean
SD	Standard Deviation
ABTS	2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonicacid
DPPH	2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl

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